

Barriers to Reading and Writing Development in Grade Learners Through the Lens of Seasoned Teachers

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Abstract. This study focused on the underlying difficulties that affect Grade 2 learners' ability to read and write, as observed by experienced educators. Despite efforts to promote early literacy, many young learners continue to encounter challenges that hinder their progress in developing essential reading and writing skills. Through semi-structured interviews with qualified and seasoned teachers, this research identifies key factors such as limited vocabulary, weak phonemic awareness, and varying levels of parental involvement as significant barriers to literacy development during the early years of schooling. Furthermore, the study examines how these teachers respond to such challenges in their classrooms. Findings highlight that strategies like inclusive instruction, differentiated learning, and targeted interventions play an essential role in supporting struggling learners, particularly those who are categorized as English Learners 2. The insights from these experienced teachers reveal that professional expertise and instructional flexibility are instrumental in addressing the diverse needs of students in reading and writing development. The study also emphasizes the practical implications of teacher experience in managing literacy-related difficulties. It offers recommendations for improving literacy instruction at the primary level and encourages stakeholders to consider these real-world classroom perspectives when forming policies or interventions.

KEY WORDS

1. Barriers to reading and writing development
2. grade 2 learners
3. Seasoned teachers

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1. Introduction

It is sad to think that there are still students who do not know how to read and write, and this is for many different reasons. The acquisition of writing skills is considered one of the most significant achievements in a young child's education process since it creates vitally important prerequisites for further academic performance and interpersonal interaction. Writing at the Grade 2 level, learners are in a transitional phase from learning to writing simple words and ending with writing more complicated sentences. Call them literacy skills, but reading and writing are the most essential activities that shape the foundation of the child's learning process. In the learning cluster outlined for the development of the Grade 2 writing standards, students are to gain further improvement in literacy skills as they shift from learning to read and write as processes to learning to read and write as tools for learning across the curriculum. However, not all these students find it as easy to acquire these crucial skills as others. Some face

some challenges that limit their learning, making it hard for them to fulfill the literacy levels that their grade should offer. On a global scale, the barriers to reading and writing development in early grades highlight several key challenges and strategies. Teachers often lack specific training in identifying and addressing reading and writing difficulties (Akyol et al., 2021). Common student challenges include spelling, unclear pronunciation, letter recognition problems, and difficulty composing sentences. These difficulties include a lack of parental support, excessive screen time, and students' preference for play over learning. Effective teacher strategies involve using varied learning methods, creating conducive learning environments, and providing individualized tutoring (Umayah, 2023). A structured approach to addressing reading and writing delays includes identifying difficulties, consulting with colleagues, guided reading and writing exercises, and regular assessments (Tsanizulfa et al., 2022). While inclusive education is generally supported, additional support for struggling students is emphasized (Akyol et al., 2021). In addition to global context, Spear-Swerling, L. (2024) describes, the patterns of reading difficulty as providing an educationally helpful way to think about different kinds of reading problems, whether those problems are mainly experiential and those familiar among English learners or associated with disabilities. Additional factors that affect reading barriers in children are mistakes in recognizing words and recognizing letters, mispronouncing, changing places, not recognizing words, and rushing when reading. In addition, showing the behavior of refusing to read, crying, or trying to fight teachers or parents can become obstacles to reading for students. Students who have difficulty learning to read show low learning outcomes in other subjects (Rohimah, 2021). Research indicates that early grade learners face numerous barriers to developing reading and writing skills, particularly in multilingual contexts. These barriers include language difficulties, poor socioeconomic environments, lack of parental involvement, and low parental education levels (Lyimo, 2023). Teachers report challenges in addressing these barriers, citing a lack of specific competencies and insufficient time for individual learners (Mavuso, 2020). Home factors, such as engaging children in numerous household activities and limited access to reading materials, also hinder literacy acquisition. Despite these challenges, teachers generally adopt a balanced approach to literacy instruction, focusing on both technical and learning-oriented dimensions (Sandberg Norling, 2018). To overcome these barriers, researchers recommend increased collaboration between teachers, parents, and the community, as well as enhanced cooperation between education departments and higher education institutions (Lyimo, 2023). In the Philippines, research on reading and writing challenges among Filipino students highlights several key issues. Poor reading abilities are attributed to lack of resources and socioeconomic factors (Idulog et al., 2023). Students struggle with recognizing text patterns, evaluating coherence, and vocabulary knowledge. Writing challenges include insufficient background knowledge, improper citation practices, and grammatical errors (Urbano et al., 2021). However, reading strategies can mediate the relationship between writing competency and class participation (Ayog Oliva, 2023). Factors facilitating scientific literacy skills development include teacher support, learning environment, and school administrative support (Palines Ortega-Dela Cruz, 2021). Recommendations for improvement include promoting early literacy programs, investing in teacher training, developing culturally relevant materials (Idulog et al., 2023), utilizing explicit instruction, and incorporating authentic tasks these findings underscore the need for targeted interventions to enhance reading and writing skills among Filipino students. In ad-

dition, significant challenges in early literacy education in the Philippines. Teachers struggle to address learning gaps in literacy and numeracy among Grade 2 students who lacked prior in-person instruction due to disruptions in traditional schooling (Makig-Angay Ligan, 2024). Kindergarten teachers also report difficulties in developing phonemic awareness among learners, with socioeconomic disparities further hindering reading and writing development (Lagrama, 2024). The transition to remote learning has demanded rapid adaptation from educators, yet many still face difficulties in implementing effective online teaching strategies (Nimer Napil, 2024). These challenges underscore the need for targeted interventions, improved teaching strategies, and better access to resources to ensure that young learners develop essential literacy skills despite educational setbacks. Furthermore, teachers face barriers to professional development, including financial and time constraints, lack of motivation, and insufficient logistical support which affect their ability to address literacy challenges (Chin et al., 2022). To overcome these challenges, educators are implementing multisensory learning approaches, targeted interventions, and encouraging greater parental involvement. Experts recommend curriculum adjustments, improved educational infrastructure, and continuous professional development programs to support teachers in enhancing their instructional methods (Makig-Angay Ligan, 2024; Chin et al., 2022). Addressing these concerns is essential for fostering effective teaching strategies and ensuring quality educa-

1.1. Purpose of the Study—This qualitative study explores the barriers to reading and writing development among Grade 2 students from teachers' perspectives. By analyzing teachers' firsthand experiences and observations, the study seeks to uncover young learners' most common obstacles and strategies teachers employ to address these barriers. Teachers' in-

tion, ultimately benefiting both educators and students in the long run. In the local context, recent studies have highlighted various barriers to reading and writing development among elementary students in Davao De Oro and similar contexts. Students experience difficulties with fundamental reading skills at school, lack family assistance, and language transition obstacles that interfere with their literacy development according to Almagro et al., (2024). On the other hand, English teachers encounter multiple obstacles when teaching writing to students because they need to help students develop their idea structure while correcting their grammar errors and motivating student participation. A phenomenological research approach at DepEd, Davao de Oro examined the actual teaching experiences of English teachers regarding writing instruction. Teachers experienced difficulties in writing revision grammar structure illustrations and writing strategy reinforcement because of resource shortages and time limitations (Cenabre Idul, 2024). To address these obstacles, educators employ strategies such as delegation, hands-on activities, and parental involvement, while also allocating resources for differentiated learning programs. Studies suggest that continuous practice, contextualized materials, and alternative reading and writing approaches are effective in sustaining students' interest in reading and writing. Strengthening reading and writing practices and fostering greater parental engagement are crucial in ensuring long-term improvements in literacy among diverse learners.

sights can offer a comprehensive view of both the challenges within the classroom, such as curriculum demands or limited resources, and those outside of it, like socio-economic factors or home support. Additionally, this research will highlight any adaptive strategies teachers find particularly compelling in overcoming these barriers. Understanding these bar-

riers is crucial for creating more inclusive and supportive literacy programs. Teacher insights can inform educational policy and program development, enabling educators, administrators, and policymakers to design interventions that cater to the diverse needs of young learners. Identifying and addressing these obstacles early makes supporting students in their foundational literacy journey possible, laying a solid groundwork for future academic success. To achieve this objective, the study will focus on several key areas. First, it identifies common barriers,

classroom-based challenges, external factors, teachers' adaptive strategies, and implications for literacy programs. By evaluating these key areas, the research will assess how well they meet the needs of students and educators alike. Second, it will identify educators' challenges. Finally, the study will propose strategies for overcoming these obstacles, aiming to provide practical recommendations for educators seeking to enhance their teaching methods through technology.

1.2. Research Questions—This study explores the teachers' experiences supporting the reading and writing literacy of Grade 2 students and gets teachers' insight from their experiences. Specifically, it seeks to answer the following questions:

- (1) What are teachers' experiences supporting the reading and writing literacy of Grade 2 students?
- (2) How do teachers cope with the challenges of developing reading and writing skills among Grade 2 students?
- (3) What educational insight can be drawn from the study?

1.3. Definition of Terms—Teachers

The findings of this research can help educate teachers about difficulties that are most likely to prevent the progress of reading and writing skills in their Grade 2 learners. In a way, the study shows how teachers from the participating schools make the classroom a more favorable environment for children with literacy difficulties, and the results offer real-life strategies that can be helpful for other educators when catering to the needs of learners with learning disabilities. Learners In Grade 2 are the other beneficiaries of the study. However, in a third-party way, teachers modify their practices based on the study results when handling students with literacy difficulties. By receiving a larger

amount of focused attention from their instructors, learners can acquire enhanced information literacy skills, academic self-esteem, and a better foundation for future academic achievement in reading and writing. For a more comprehensive understanding, the following terms are defined operationally:

Seasoned Teachers

Refer to educators who have accumulated a substantial amount of experience in teaching. Operationally, this is often defined as teachers with more than 5-10 years of classroom experience. Their teaching journey has allowed them to observe, adapt, and refine their instructional strategies, as well as to understand diverse student needs.

1.4. Significant of the Study—The study titled "Barriers to Reading and Writing Devel-

opment in Grade in Grade Learner: A Qualitative Analysis of Teachers' Experiences" offers valuable benefits for a range of stakeholders:

1.5. Theoretical Lens—

This study anchored the Constructivist Theory rooted in the work of psychologists Jean Piaget (197) and Lev Vygotsky (1978), who both emphasized the importance of learning through experience. This theory emphasizes how learners build knowledge through experiences. It can help explore how students' developmental stages or backgrounds affect their ability to read and write. Piaget's theory of cognitive development emphasizes that individuals actively construct their understanding of the world through experiences, interactions, and reflections. Vygotsky's theory of socio-cultural development highlights the role of social interactions in cognitive development and the importance of scaffolding or providing support to students as they learn new skills. In the constructivist approach, the teacher designs activities and assessments encouraging students to engage in meaningful, authentic tasks. Teacher provides feedback and guidance but allows students to lead the learning process. The focus is on helping students understand the why and how of the material rather than simply memorizing information. The constructivist approach recognizes that learning is a personal and ongoing process and seeks to empower students as active participants in their education. Constructivism is a new approach in education that claims humans can better understand the information they have constructed by themselves. According to constructivist theories, learning is a social advancement that involves language, real-world situations, and interaction and collaboration among learners. The learners are considered to be central to the learning process. Learning is affected by our prejudices, experiences, the time we live, and physical and mental maturity. When motivated, the learner exercises his will, determination, and action to gather selective information, convert it, formulate hypotheses, test these suppositions via applications, interactions, experiences, and draw verifiable conclusions. Constructivism transforms today's classrooms

into a knowledge-construction site where information is absorbed and knowledge is built by the learner (Sharma Shukla, 2023). In addition, this study also anchored Ecological System Theory by Urie Bronfenbrenner in 1979. This theory explores how various environmental factors (family, school, community) influence a child's development. It is relevant for identifying barriers to literacy that arise from factors beyond the classroom. This theory looks at a child's development within the context of the system of relationships that form his or her environment. Bronfenbrenner's theory defines complex "layers" of the environment, each affecting a child's development. This theory has recently been renamed "bioecological systems theory" to emphasize that a child's biology is a primary environment fueling her development. The interaction between factors in the child's maturing biology, his immediate family/community environment, and the societal landscape fuels and steers his development. Changes or conflicts in any one layer will ripple throughout other layers. To study a child's development, we must look at the child, her immediate environment, and her interaction with the larger environment (Bronfenbrenner Ryan, 2001). Figure 1 presents the conceptual framework of the study. It shows three interconnected working themes. The experiences of educators in developing students' writing and reading literacy focus on how educators encounter and address challenges in helping students develop literacy skills. Insights of educators in developing students' writing and reading literacy include educators' reflections and understanding of effective methods in literacy development and coping mechanisms of educators in developing students writing and reading literacy that explore the strategies teachers use to overcome barriers in promoting reading and writing skills among students. These themes relate to educators' experiences fostering student reading and writing literacy.

Fig. 1. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework

2. Methodology

In this study, I adopted a qualitative research design, drawing from a phenomenological approach to better understand how teachers perceive and experience the process of supporting second-grade students in developing literacy, particularly in reading and writing. My intention was to explore the challenges they encounter and the factors that may limit students’ progress in acquiring these essential skills. By focusing on Grade 2 learners, I aimed to highlight the real-world classroom dynamics and teaching strategies that shape early literacy development from the teachers’ point of view. In conducting this study, I recognized that qualitative methods offer various tools for exploring human experiences. Among these, focus group discussions, in-depth interviews, and participant observation are commonly utilized, each suited to different types of data. For example, participant observation allowed me to observe natural behaviors in real-life contexts, while in-depth interviews were particularly useful for gaining deep insights into individuals’ personal histories, perspectives, and emotions especially when sensitive issues were involved. On the other hand, focus groups helped generate collective viewpoints and revealed shared values and concerns within specific cultural groups or communities. To guide my study, I employed phenomenology as the research approach, which centers on uncovering and interpreting individuals lived experiences (Badil et al., 2023). Rather than analyzing reality from an outside perspective, phenomenology emphasizes the importance of understanding how people perceive and make meaning of their world. This concept, introduced by Edmund Husserl, argues that we must explore the world through the lens of personal experience. Later, thinkers like Amedeo Giorgi and Clark Moustakas adapted these ideas for use in psychology and social sciences. Gaining familiarity with the philosophical and psychological foundations of phenomenology has been essential in shaping how I applied this approach to my research (McCoog, 2021).

2.1. *Philosophical Assumptions*—In shaping my research design, I grounded the process of data collection, analysis, and interpretation within a clear philosophical framework. This

foundational structure helped ensure that the findings and conclusions were firmly rooted in the context of the study. In the sections that follow, I explain the core philosophical assumptions that informed the direction of the research. These assumptions played a vital role in guiding both the theoretical orientation and the practical methodology, especially within the domains of communication and education. Drawing from the work of Khalifa and Khalifa (2024), I acknowledged four key perspectives ontological, epistemological, axiological, and methodological which collectively shaped how I approached and understood the inquiry throughout the research process.

Ontological Assumption In this study, I engaged with the concept of ontology to explore the fundamental nature of reality as it applied to my research topic. Ontology, as described by Bisel and Adame (2017), involves understanding beliefs about what exists and what constitutes reality. From a qualitative standpoint, I embraced the idea that multiple realities exist, as supported by Khalifa and Khalifa (2024). Their work underscores the importance of acknowledging diverse perspectives and experiences, which is why I made it a point to highlight a wide range of participant voices. To reflect this ontological stance, I collected and analyzed data in a way that captured varied lived experiences. I used rich participant quotes and identified recurring and emerging themes that pointed to the existence of different realities. As I worked through the responses, I coded them thoroughly looking not only for patterns across participants but also for the unique aspects of each individual's perspective. This careful process allowed me to preserve the authenticity of their voices while maintaining the integrity and trustworthiness of the data, free from personal bias.

Epistemological Assumption In this study, I viewed epistemology as a framework for understanding how knowledge is constructed, interpreted, and acquired. Within psychology, epistemo-

logical inquiry often involves examining the distinction between justified belief and opinion, as well as exploring cognitive processes that underpin how individuals come to know what they know (Babajanyan, 2020). I adopted a social constructionist stance, which shaped the way I understood my role in relation to the participants (Lawson, 2021). This perspective was well-aligned with the qualitative nature of my research, as it emphasized co-constructing meaning through active engagement and reflective dialogue. Scholars such as Arseven et al. (2021) have even developed instruments like the Epistemological Belief Scale (EBS) to assess individuals' beliefs about knowledge and knowing. Beyond the social sciences, epistemological assumptions also play a role in other fields for example, Hubert Dreyfus contributed significantly to epistemological debates in artificial intelligence by emphasizing the importance of bodily experience and cognitive function in knowledge formation (Su Luvaanjalba, 2021). Understanding epistemological foundations is vital across disciplines such as psychology, education, and artificial intelligence, as it informs how researchers' approach, generate, and apply knowledge in both theory and practice. For this research, I engaged directly with participants to gather deep, contextual insights. These close interactions helped me interpret not just the content of their responses but also the experiences that shaped their understanding. This process enabled me to frame the study in a way that highlighted the dynamic relationship between myself as the researcher and the individuals whose voices and realities I sought to represent.

Axiological Assumption

The concept of axiology centers on the role of values in research, particularly in determining what is deemed important, appropriate, or ethically significant within a study (Khalifa Khalifa, 2024). In the context of qualitative research, Khalifa and Khalifa (2024) emphasized that researchers' values and belief systems in-

evitably influence the research process—from the development of research questions to data interpretation. They highlighted the idea that qualitative inquiry is inherently value-laden, with the potential for researcher bias to shape the study’s direction and findings. In my own research, I acknowledged the impact of personal and participant values on the data gathered. I made a conscious effort to honor the dignity and significance of each participant’s contribution. I recognized that the narratives shared during interviews were shaped not only by the participants’ lived experiences but also by their individual value systems. At the same time, I remained aware of my own positionality and how it might affect the interpretation of those narratives. Throughout the process, I thoughtfully evaluated participant feedback within the broader context of their experiences, ensuring that their voices were respectfully represented and not overshadowed by my own preconceptions.

Rhetorical Assumption This study was grounded in the methodological assumption that reality should be understood through the perspectives of the participants. Rather than prioritizing traditional quantitative criteria such as internal and external validity or objectivity, I approached the research with a focus on qualitative measures of trustworthiness—namely, cred-

2.2. Qualitative Assumptions—In conducting this study, I employed a qualitative phenomenological approach and utilized in-depth interviews as my primary method of data collection. This strategy was appropriate for exploring the unique perspectives and lived experiences of the participants in relation to the phenomenon under investigation. In-depth interviews are widely recognized in the social sciences for their ability to provide rich, comprehensive insights into individuals’ thoughts, feelings, and interpretations of their social world (Barrick, 2020).

ibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability. I used a personal, reflective voice throughout the process to remain authentic and engaged with the lived realities shared by the participants. To explore the experiences, challenges, and insights of school staff and employees involved in crisis-management efforts, I employed a phenomenological research design. This approach allowed me to address complex, real-world issues in a way that respected the uniqueness of each participant’s perspective (Badil et al., 2023). By adopting phenomenology, I was able to develop a deeper understanding of the phenomenon under investigation, interpret the meanings embedded in participants’ experiences, and generate insights grounded in their narratives. Phenomenological research, as described by Neubauer, Witkop, and Varpio (2019), emphasizes understanding the world from the viewpoint of individuals who have personally lived through a specific event or circumstance. In alignment with this principle, I conducted in-depth interviews and engaged in ongoing data analysis to illuminate not only what participants experienced, but also how they experienced it. This iterative, immersive approach allowed me to construct a rich, meaningful interpretation of the phenomenon based on the voices of those directly involved.

These interviews are typically open-ended and allow for exploratory discussions, often conducted with a relatively small number of participants. Among the different formats structured, semi-structured, and unstructured I opted for semi-structured interviews to strike a balance between consistency and flexibility in data gathering. Qualitative research interviews have long been considered essential tools in social science inquiries (McGrath et al., 2018). In my case, interviews enabled me to directly engage participants and gain access to their views and per-

sonal narratives. As noted by Hinton and Ryan (2019), such interviews are particularly effective in uncovering personal meanings and interpretations. Moreover, they allow for a deeper understanding of a subject through the voices of a relatively small but information-rich group (Young et al., 2018). I viewed each interview as a dynamic social interaction an exchange

2.3. Design and Procedure—In this research, I adopted a qualitative design, specifically using phenomenology, to deeply explore and interpret the lived experiences of participants. This approach enabled me to focus on the real-world challenges and personal insights of educators engaged in contractual teaching arrangements. Depending on feasibility and availability, participants took part in either face-to-face or virtual focus group discussions. After data collection, I analyzed the responses by identifying recurring themes and patterns that emerged from the participants' narratives. I chose phenomenology as it allowed me to center the study on the participants' subjective experiences and meanings. Thematic analysis was employed within this framework to interpret the data. Before participating, each individual signed an informed consent form. They were assured that they could withdraw from the study at any time if they felt uncomfortable, ensuring voluntary and ethical participation. Throughout the research process, I strictly followed ethical standards and adhered to applicable safety and health protocols. Qualitative research, by its nature, is iterative and aims to develop a deep understanding of complex human behaviors and experiences by closely engaging with the phenomenon under investigation (Aspers Corte, 2019). As the primary instrument of the research, I applied various qualitative methods such as interviews and focus group discus-

of dialogue in which I posed thoughtful questions and listened intently to the responses, as Roulston (2018) described. This method proved especially useful in capturing the complexity of the issues being explored, particularly those involving diverse perspectives and value systems (Hillman, 2022).

sions—while remaining conscious of my role in shaping the inquiry (Awasthy, 2019). This approach also served to generate valuable insights and refine understanding within the academic community (Aspers Corte, 2019). To gather in-depth responses, I developed a semi-structured interview guide that served as a flexible tool during interviews. This guide helped me explore specific research questions while allowing room for additional, spontaneous insights. I used an audio recorder to ensure the accuracy of the transcripts and data interpretation. The questions were aligned with the central research objectives and designed to reveal themes and meanings crucial to the study. To ensure the credibility of the research design and instruments, I consulted with research specialists and submitted the interview guide for expert validation. Their feedback helped refine the tool and enhance the quality of data collection. Participant selection was carried out using purposive sampling, a non-probability sampling technique commonly used in qualitative research. This approach involved identifying and inviting educators who met specific criteria relevant to the study's objectives (Campbell et al., 2020). Participants were selected through a referral system based on predetermined qualifications. Throughout the study, I upheld the principles of confidentiality and ethical responsibility. I treated each participant's identity with respect and maintained professionalism in all research interactions.

2.4. Research Participants—

The participants of my study were teachers from Camanlangan Elementary School in New Bataan, Davao de Oro. I purposively selected eight (8) teachers with at least six years of teaching experience at the said institution specifically, four Grade 1 and four Grade 2 teachers who handled reading and writing subjects. When the number of qualified participants was insufficient, I expanded the participant pool to include neighboring schools within the district, such as Tandawan Integrated School, Magangit Integrated School, La Purisima Elementary School, and San Isidro Elementary School. According to Andrade (2020), purposive sampling was appropriate because it allowed for the selection of participants with direct experience

2.5. Ethical Considerations—This research study adhered strictly to established ethical standards and fully complied with the provisions outlined in the Data Privacy Act of 2012 to safeguard the confidentiality and privacy of all participant information. Fundamental ethical protocols including obtaining informed consent, ensuring voluntary participation, and recognizing each participant's right to withdraw at any stage were consistently observed throughout the research process. To further protect participant anonymity, pseudonyms were assigned in all data transcripts and written outputs. Ethical considerations were treated as essential components of the study, given their importance in maintaining the integrity and credibility of the research. Upholding these standards was vital to presenting accurate findings grounded in truth and free from researcher bias. Social Value

In this study, I focused on the perspectives of experienced teachers to gain a deeper understanding of the barriers that hinder the development of reading and writing skills among elementary learners. The aim was to generate insights that could inform improvements in in-

relevant to the research topic, thereby ensuring the collection of rich and meaningful data. In my study, I used a purposive sampling design since participants were selected based on specific criteria aligned with the study's objectives. In qualitative research, purposive sampling also known as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling is a non-probability sampling method often employed when selecting individuals who can provide in-depth insights into a particular phenomenon (Etikan et al., 2022). This approach was particularly effective for gaining a comprehensive understanding of a specific experience, event, or context (Campbell et al., 2020).

structional strategies, curriculum planning, and educational policies designed to support sustained literacy growth. The findings of this research are intended to benefit not only classroom teachers but also school leaders, policy-makers, and parents who share a common goal of enhancing students' academic success. By emphasizing literacy as a foundational skill, the study advocates for its role in enabling children to access lifelong learning opportunities, achieve upward social mobility, and benefit from equitable access to quality education.

Informed Consent

Before initiating the phenomenological research process and reaching out to participants for interviews, I ensured that each individual received and fully understood an informed consent form. Prior to any data collection, participants were required to provide written acknowledgment and explicit agreement to participate in the study. The informed consent letter served several purposes: it introduced the research topic, provided background information, identified me as the researcher along with my contact details, and clearly outlined the study's aims and objectives. It also emphasized partic-

participants' right to decline or withdraw from the study at any point without any consequences. Additionally, the letter explained the nature of the information expected from them. Only after signing and submitting the informed consent form were participants formally included in the research. The Vulnerability of Research Participants The participants in this study served as the primary sources of information and demonstrated reliability in completing the research tool. To address any possible questions or clarifications regarding the study, I ensured that my contact information was made available to all participants throughout the research process. Risks, Benefits, and Safety The participants in this study were selected voluntarily, without any form of bribery, coercion, or undue influence. They were also provided with the contact information of the research panel for any inquiries or concerns related to the study. If participants experienced discomfort or inconvenience while responding to any questions, they were not obligated to answer and were allowed to skip to the next item. Furthermore, participants retained the right to withdraw from the study at any point without consequence. To ensure the safety and comfort of participants during the interview process, the researcher conducted data collection in secure and accessible locations. The study prioritized the Treaty Principle of Protection, which emphasized safeguarding the privacy and confidentiality of all respondents. Pseudonyms were assigned to protect participant identities, and all necessary precautions were taken to minimize potential risks and maintain ethical standards throughout the research process. Privacy and Confidentiality of Information The study strictly adhered to the provisions of the Data Privacy Act of 2012, ensuring that all participant information remained confidential and could not be traced back to any individual. To safeguard participant identities, the researcher implemented measures to uphold anonymity throughout the research process. All printed and digital ma-

terials generated from the study were securely stored in a restricted-access environment. Moreover, the researcher proactively addressed potential conflicts of interest to preserve the integrity of the study. Care was also taken to avoid any form of data misrepresentation or biased interpretation, thereby maintaining the accuracy and objectivity of the research findings.

Justice During the data collection phase, participants were thoroughly informed of both the researcher's responsibilities and their own roles in the study. Emphasis was placed on the importance of providing honest and accurate responses to the interview questions to ensure the credibility of the findings. All interactions and communications related to the research were conducted with transparency and integrity. Furthermore, participants were made aware that the primary aim of the study was to benefit them by contributing to insights and recommendations that could enhance their professional practice and educational experiences. Transparency After the study was completed, the findings were shared with participants and school administrators to promote transparency and uphold ethical standards. The results were provided using a flash drive or other preferred formats, depending on the participants' requests. The study's outcomes offered valuable insights for elementary teachers, school administrators, and curriculum developers by highlighting key issues relevant to literacy development and educational practice. Participants were reminded of their right to withdraw at any point before the conclusion of the data collection phase. They were also given the opportunity to review their interview transcripts and request corrections or removal of any identifying information. To ensure anonymity during data analysis and reporting, the researcher used pseudonyms, modified names, and adjusted non-critical dates, thereby safeguarding participants' confidentiality. Qualification of the Researcher I possessed the necessary qualifications to conduct the study, having completed all academic

requirements and passed the comprehensive examination. This research was part of the requirements for earning my master's degree. I was fully prepared physically, mentally, emotionally, and financially—to carry out the study. Additionally, the collaboration between my adviser and me greatly contributed to the successful completion of the research. Adequacy of Facilities I completed the study within the specified timeframe using all the necessary resources. The research panel contributed to improving the quality of the paper by offering valuable suggestions and recommendations. Additionally, I ensured that there was sufficient funding available to support the continuation and successful completion of the research. Community Involvement I honored the participants' local traditions, culture, and perspectives throughout the study. I did not use any form of deception

2.6. Role of the Researcher—I adopted both observational and interactive roles throughout the study process, beginning with securing formal approvals from the Schools Division Superintendent and the heads of the participating schools. This ensured that the research was conducted ethically and with the collaboration of the educational institutions involved. By establishing these professional relationships, I laid a foundation of trust that was essential to maintaining the integrity of the study. During the data collection phase, I actively engaged in fa-

2.7. Data Collection—The following will be the step-by-step process of gathering the data the researcher needs. Asking for the Endorsement Letter from the Dean I requested an endorsement letter from the dean, as obtaining this letter was a crucial step in the research process. It demonstrated that my study complied with the university's standards of academic conduct and ethical practices. This endorsement granted

during its implementation, particularly in participant recruitment or data collection procedures. I believed it was essential to express my genuine enthusiasm and commitment to wholehearted participation in the research process.

Plagiarism and Fabrication as the Researcher I showed respect for the works and intellectual properties of others by properly citing authors and rephrasing in my own words what others had expressed. Furthermore, I made sure to comprehend the context of each study and refrained from directly copying text from reference papers. I consistently used citations to indicate that the text had been borrowed from another source. Moreover, I ensured honesty while working on the manuscript and did not intentionally misrepresent or fabricate data and results, nor did I purposefully present inaccurate conclusions.

cilitating in-depth interviews and group discussions, while striving to maintain objectivity in analyzing the data. This commitment to neutrality was vital to ensuring that the findings were both reliable and aligned with the research framework. My approach enabled a deeper understanding of the participants' lived experiences and insights. Through meaningful dialogue and careful observation of relevant texts, I aimed to construct a comprehensive interpretation of the data that accurately captured the complexities of the participants' realities.

me formal permission to collect data from participants and significantly enhanced my credibility. When individuals and institutions were informed that the study had received official approval, they were more willing to cooperate, which provided me with better access to the necessary resources for conducting the research. Asking Permission from the School Administrators and Principal To conduct the study in the

identified educational institution, I wrote a formal letter to the School Division Superintendent, attaching Chapters 1 and 2 of my manuscript along with the research instrument. In the letter, I explained the objectives of the study and identified the intended participants. After sending the documents, I waited for the responses and approval from the School Administrators and the Principal before proceeding with the data collection. Obtaining Consent from the Participants I requested the participants' permission and provided them with a formal orientation about the study and their role in the process as participants. Conducting the Interview After obtaining informed consent from the participants, I conducted a focus group discussion using a semi-structured interview guide. I recorded the

participants' demographics and, with their consent, took notes and recorded the conversations using my cell phone for easier transcription. I actively listened and engaged with the participants throughout the session. Transcribing the Responses of the Interviewees I accurately transcribed the interviewees' responses by listening to their answers from the cell phone's audio recorder. Since the participants were encouraged to use a language they were comfortable with, I translated non-English responses into English. Data Coding and Thematic Analysis After transcribing the data, I categorized and coded it. Subsequently, I extracted themes and compared and contrasted the participants' individual data to identify patterns and trends.

2.8. Data Analysis—I utilized thematic analysis to examine the collected data and assess the responses of the interview participants. Thematic analysis is a popular qualitative research method used to identify patterns

and themes in data (Fuchs, 2023). It focuses on identifying patterns and generating themes (Lochmiller, 2021). This method provides flexibility and theoretical freedom while offering rich, detailed analytical accounts (Majumdar, 2019).

2.9. Framework of Analysis—The framework for this study allows for flexibility, enabling data collection and analysis to coincide. Data gathered from Contractual teachers will be reviewed and organized according to recurring topics and themes related to their experiences, challenges, and insights. Drawing from the steps outlined by Fuchs (2023), The process typically involves six steps: getting familiar with the data, generating initial codes, searching for themes, reviewing the themes, defining and naming the themes, and producing a report. This process ensures that the analysis remains focused on capturing teachers' experiences and struggles in working in a contractual arrangement. Familiarization In this initial stage, I became acquainted with the data by reading and

re-reading it while noting any initial analytical observation. Coding Coding was a process I commonly used in various qualitative analysis methods. It involved creating brief labels for significant data features relevant to the overall research question. Coding was not just a technique for reducing data; it was also an analytical process. The codes represented a semantic and conceptual interpretation of the data. I assigned a code to each piece of data and concluded this stage by organizing all the codes along with their associated data extracts.

Searching In this stage, I identified coherent and meaningful patterns within the data that related to the research question. I finished this stage by categorizing all the coded data according to each identified theme. Reviewing I as-

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study)

sessed whether the themes effectively communicated a compelling narrative about the data. This involved delineating each theme’s essence and exploring their interconnections. Defining and Naming I analyzed each theme in detail, identified its core components, and created concise, impactful, and informative titles for each theme.

Producing

2.10. *Trustworthiness of the Study*—In qualitative research, the concepts of validity and reliability are not commonly emphasized. Instead, I focused on establishing the trustwor-

The report involved weaving together the analytic narrative and data extracts to tell the reader a coherent and persuasive story about the data Figure 2 shows that the framework offers a systematic approach to analyzing qualitative data, ensuring that the results are extracted in an organized manner and interpreted in a meaningful way.

thiness of the data, which is considered essential for ensuring quality and rigor in qualitative studies. According to Harts (2019), trustworthiness consists of credibility, transferability, de-

pendability, and confirmability. Credibility Referred to the extent to which the findings of my research were believable and accurately represented the participants lived experiences. I ensured credibility by aligning my interpretations closely with the perspectives shared by the participants and by seeking their agreement on the meanings derived from the data. Transferability Meant that the insights from my study could potentially be applied to other similar settings or groups. I supported transferability by providing rich, detailed descriptions of the research context and participants, allowing other researchers or readers to determine the applicability of the

findings to their own situations.

Dependability Focused on the consistency of the study's results. To address this, I documented all the procedures I followed so that other researchers could replicate the study under similar conditions and arrive at comparable findings. Confirmability Referred to the objectivity of the research process. I ensured that the findings were shaped by the participants' responses rather than my own biases. This was achieved through careful documentation and, where possible, external validation of the data by independent reviewers to confirm the accuracy and relevance of the interpretations.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents and discusses the key findings of the study. This research explored the barriers that hinder the development of reading and writing skills among grade-level learners, as perceived and experienced by seasoned teachers. It highlights the real-life encounters, insights, and challenges these educators face in supporting literacy growth. The findings of the study are presented through emerging themes that were derived from a thematic analysis of interview data. These themes were interpreted in light of relevant educational theories and existing literature to provide deeper understanding and context to the results.

3.1. Experiences of Teachers Supporting Grade 2 Students Literacy—It explores how teachers help young learners develop essential literacy skills during a critical stage in their education. It focuses on the methods they use to teach reading and writing, the challenges they face such as varied student abilities, limited resources, or time constraints and the strategies they apply to overcome these difficulties. Grade 2 is a crucial period where students transition from learning to read to reading to learn, making the teacher's role highly influential. By understanding teachers' real-life classroom experiences, this topic provides valuable insights into improving literacy instruction, enhancing student outcomes, and informing educational support and training. Below are the themes and responses of teachers in their experiences in supporting reading and writing literacy of grade 2

students.

3.1.1. Enhancing Learners' Skills—Real-life experiences of teachers, schools, or educational programs that have effectively improved students' academic or practical abilities. It focuses on the positive outcomes achieved through innovative teaching strategies, student-centered approaches, or supportive learning environments. These stories may involve students overcoming learning difficulties, mastering key skills like reading, writing, or problem-solving, and gaining confidence in their abilities. By sharing these successes, the topic aims to inspire educators, showcase best practices, and emphasize the importance of dedication, creativity, and collaboration in achieving meaningful learning progress. Online learning approaches have shown effectiveness in developing reading and writing literacy skills for second-grade

students, focusing on activities such as reading aloud, comprehension, and simple text composition (Novita et al., 2021). Critical literacy skills, essential for young learners in the 21st century, can be fostered through sustainable implementation designs for grades 1-6, incorporating activities like finding clues, completing pictures, and reading diaries. These studies collectively emphasize the importance of diverse, engaging literacy activities in supporting cognitive skills development, including critical thinking, problem-solving, and creativity in early primary education.

3.1.2. Using Different Assessment Techniques—The various methods and tools educators use to evaluate student learning, progress, and understanding. It includes both formative assessments like quizzes, class activities, and observations used during learning and summative assessments like final tests or projects used after instruction. The focus is on how teachers choose, implement, and adapt these techniques to suit different learners' needs and ensure fair, accurate evaluations. This topic also highlights how assessment results guide teachers in improving instruction, providing feedback, and supporting student growth and achievement. To effectively assess students' writing performance, teachers emphasize the importance of evaluating a variety of samples based on fluency, content conventions, syntax, and vocabulary. Teacher 2 explained that assessing writing across multiple purposes and genres provides a comprehensive understanding of students' capabilities in different text structures. In monitoring reading and writing development, Teacher 3 shared the use of both formal and informal assessment methods. These include standardized quizzes for formal evaluation and informal strategies like observation, checklists, and peer reviews to track students' progress more holistically. This blended approach allows for a well-rounded insight into the learners' growth in literacy. Research suggests that assessing

student writing across various genres and contexts provides a more comprehensive picture of writing performance. Studies have examined writing samples from different settings, including standardized assessments and university courses as well as multiple genres like essays, critiques, and case studies (Goulart et al., 2022). Findings indicate that texts often serve multiple communicative purposes, with considerable variation within genres. Training programs focusing on multiple genres and audiences have shown promise in improving graduate students' writing skills across different formats (Harrington et al., 2021). In high school settings, reports, book reviews, and news articles are commonly used for writing assessments, but implementation of rubrics and evaluation criteria can vary significantly across subjects (Lee, 2024). These studies highlight the importance of considering diverse writing contexts, clear task definitions, and well-designed rubrics when assessing student writing across different text structures and genres. This indicates that assessing student writing performance across various genres and purposes is crucial for obtaining a comprehensive picture of writing abilities. These findings underscore the need for diverse writing samples across different text structures and genres to provide a complete and reliable assessment of students' writing performance.

3.1.3. Mixing Effective Strategies—Teachers combine different teaching methods and approaches to enhance student learning and engagement in the classroom. Instead of relying on just one technique, educators blend strategies such as direct instruction, group work, hands-on activities, technology integration, and individualized support to address diverse learning styles and needs. This approach allows for more flexible, responsive teaching and can lead to better academic outcomes, improved student motivation, and a more dynamic learning environment. By mixing effective strategies, teachers can create well-rounded lessons that cater to all types

of learners. To foster reading and writing skills among Grade 2 learners, teachers employ various interactive and engaging strategies. Teacher 1 integrates games and activities such as word searches, crossword puzzles, and reading bingo to reinforce literacy skills. For writing, modeling effective writing styles is also emphasized. Teacher 6 enhances motivation by creating a positive reading environment, offering student choice in reading materials, and integrating writing across subject areas. Additionally, Teacher 8 highlights the significance of combining effective strategies, enjoyable activities, and parental involvement in promoting literacy, while recognizing the ongoing challenges and opportunities for professional growth. Teachers can enhance student learning and engagement by combining various teaching methods and approaches. Active learning strategies, such as collaborative learning, gamification, and problem-based learning, have been shown to improve student performance and critical thinking skills. Implementing a mix of teacher-centered and student-centered approaches can cater to different learning styles and promote deeper understanding (Levitt, et al., 2023). Heterogeneous pedagogical approaches, including short lectures, brainstorming, group reports, and technology-based activities, can positively influence student engagement and performance. These strategies help students acquire meta-cognitive knowledge and set the direction for learning (Asif et al., 2020). By incorporating diverse teaching methods, educators can create a more dynamic and effective learning environment that stimulates students' brains, expands their knowledge, and facilitates the learning process (Abulhul, 2021). These strategies can help students meet their educational needs and stimulate their brains to expand their knowledge and learning. These methods are as follows: presenting short lectures to refresh students' attention to the class lesson and help their brains come up with ideas about the topic based on their daily experience,

brainstorming that is a class group activity helping students work together and learn how to value each other opinions, group reports that encourage students to be familiar with strategies of writing a report as a conclusion for the group meeting, technology-based activities that develops students' educational skills in broadening their self-learning, and PowerPoint presentation that helps students review what they have learned in the class.

3.1.4. Experiencing Challenges due to Diversity—The difficulties teachers face in classrooms with students from different backgrounds, abilities, languages, and learning needs. Diversity can include cultural and religious differences, varied socio-economic statuses, students with disabilities, and those who speak different mother tongues. While diversity enriches the learning environment, it also presents challenges such as communication barriers, unequal access to resources, and the need for differentiated instruction. This topic highlights how these challenges affect teaching and learning, and why it's important for educators to develop inclusive strategies to ensure that all students feel supported, respected, and able to succeed. Grade 2 learners are in a stage of rapid cognitive development, yet their progress varies. Teacher 1 noted that some students struggle with phonological awareness, working memory, and other foundational cognitive skills essential for reading and writing. Additionally, students with learning disabilities such as dyslexia face significant challenges, along with issues related to short attention spans and underdeveloped fine motor skills. Teacher 3 emphasized that limited vocabulary and minimal language exposure at home affect comprehension, vocabulary growth, and expression. Motivation and sustained attention also emerge as common obstacles. Teacher 5 added that student behavior, focus, and overall interest in learning are persistent challenges that impact literacy development in the classroom. Teachers face numer-

Fig. 3. Emerging Themes on the Experiences of Teachers Supporting Grade 2 Students Literacy

ous challenges in diverse classrooms, including managing students from different cultural backgrounds, abilities, and languages. Common difficulties include classroom management, differentiation of teaching methods, language barriers, and addressing varied learning styles (Sharma, 2023). Teachers struggle with behavioral issues, students' trauma experiences, and lack of specialized materials for refugee and migrant students (Stathopoulou Dassi, 2020). Primary school teachers report problems related to themselves, students, and parents when working with culturally diverse classrooms. Secondary school teachers are more familiar with students with disabilities and more willing to adapt their methodology compared to university professors. However, they feel more insecure and demand additional training, especially for visual disabilities (Pais et al., 2020). These challenges highlight the need for ongoing support, resources, and training to help teachers effectively navigate diverse classrooms and ensure equitable educa-

tion for all students. In today's world, schools and classrooms are becoming more multicultural and inclusive. This means that students come from different backgrounds, cultures, abilities, and have different learning needs. Because of this, teachers have a very important role in making sure that all students have a good learning experience. They need to make sure that every student feels included and supported in their education. The results of this study show that many teachers face similar problems when teaching in diverse classrooms. Some of the most common challenges include managing the classroom well, using different teaching methods to meet the needs of all students, and overcoming language barriers. Teachers also struggle to understand and support the different ways that students learn. These challenges can make teaching more difficult, but they also show the importance of helping teachers become more prepared to handle these situations.

3.2. *Cope with the Challenges Faced by Teachers in Supporting Grade 2 Students' Reading and Writing Skills*—Teachers manage and overcome the difficulties they encounter while helping young learners develop literacy. These challenges may include varying reading levels, limited resources, lack of parental support, and students with learning difficulties. Despite these obstacles, teachers apply coping strategies such as using creative teaching materials, implementing individualized instruction, collaborating with parents, and seeking professional development. This topic emphasizes the resilience and adaptability of teachers as they work to build strong reading and writing foundations for their Grade 2 students. Below are the themes and responses of teachers.

3.2.1. *Using Differentiated Instruction*—Teachers adapt their teaching methods, materials, and assessments to meet the diverse needs, interests, and learning styles of their students. In a single classroom, students may learn at different paces or have varying strengths, so differentiated instruction allows teachers to provide personalized support such as offering simpler texts, visual aids, advanced tasks, or hands-on activities to ensure all learners can succeed. This approach promotes inclusivity, boosts student engagement, and helps each child reach their full potential by making learning more accessible and effective for everyone. To overcome these challenges, teachers emphasize the use of differentiated instruction. Teacher 1 shared that adapting teaching strategies through various methods and materials helps address diverse learning styles and abilities. Similarly, Teacher 2 stressed that effective implementation of differentiated instruction tailored to individual student needs, the integration of educational technology, and continuous professional development are essential in improving teaching effectiveness and student learning outcomes. Research shows that teachers can adapt their teaching methods to meet diverse student needs

through differentiated instruction (DI). This approach involves recognizing students' varied cognitive and non-cognitive readiness, learning styles, interests, talents, and experiences (Ramdani et al., 2022). Effective DI requires teachers to have both a growth mindset and an ethical compass oriented towards students. Adaptive teaching practices include modifying instructional strategies, materials, and assessments to address individual differences (Gazioglu et al., 2022). For example, physics teachers can tailor their curriculum, instruction, and assessment methods to accommodate students' varying backgrounds and abilities (Wenning Vieyra, 2020). While implementing DI can be challenging, especially for novice teachers, it allows educators to "meet students where they are" and maximize learning outcomes. Understanding student diversity is crucial for effective adaptive learning and assessment, even in resource-limited environments (Ramdani et al., 2022). Differentiated instruction is a teaching approach where teachers adjust their methods, materials, and assessments to fit the unique needs of each student. Since students have different backgrounds, abilities, interests, and ways of learning, this approach helps create a more inclusive and effective learning environment. Teachers may use various activities, groupings, or learning tools to reach students in ways that work best for them. By doing so, they can better support individual progress and help every student succeed. Differentiated instruction shows the importance of understanding each learner and providing equal opportunities for growth in a diverse and dynamic classroom setting.

3.2.2. *Supporting Colleagues*—This highlights the importance of collaboration and teamwork among teachers in creating a positive and effective teaching environment. When educators share ideas, teaching strategies, resources, and emotional support, it helps them overcome challenges, reduce stress, and improve their professional growth. This support can come

through team planning, peer mentoring, co-teaching, or simply offering encouragement during difficult times. In the context of helping students especially those struggling with reading and writing colleague support plays a vital role in building a strong network that promotes both teacher success and student learning. Through the implementation of effective strategies and seeking collaborative support, teachers are able to address the challenges in developing reading and writing skills among Grade 2 learners. Teacher 6 highlighted that by asking help from colleagues and utilizing available resources, they can navigate difficulties more effectively. Teacher 1 also emphasized the role of educational authorities in providing access to continuous professional development, such as trainings and seminars, which allow teachers to share insights, knowledge, and strategies that help overcome instructional barriers. Teacher collaboration is crucial for creating a positive school climate and improving educational outcomes. Well-functioning teacher teams provide a safe environment for developing and maintaining a supportive school atmosphere. Collaboration networks in schools can focus on different areas, including teaching improvement, team improvement, and organizational improvement (Wullschleger et al., 2023). Effective collaboration can lead to decreased isolation, supportive relationships, and enhanced content knowledge and pedagogical approaches. However, achieving successful collaboration is challenging due to factors such as leadership, interpersonal dynamics, and external pressures. Trust-based relationships that allow for constructive disagreement are essential (Weddle et al., 2020). Educational leaders play a crucial role in fostering cooperative environments. Despite challenges like teacher reluctance and lack of engagement, collaboration remains a key strategy for school improvement and student success (García-Martínez et al., 2021). Support from colleagues plays a very important role in cre-

ating a positive and effective teaching environment. When teachers work together by sharing ideas, teaching strategies, and learning materials, they are better able to face challenges and reduce stress. This teamwork also helps teachers grow professionally and feel more confident in their roles. Support can happen through team planning, mentoring, co-teaching, or simply encouraging each other during hard times. Especially when helping students who struggle with reading and writing, having strong support from fellow teachers builds a network that improves both teacher performance and student learning outcomes in the classroom.

3.2.3. *Receiving help from the Family*—

The crucial role of parental involvement in developing children's reading and writing skills. Parents serve as a child's first teacher, and their active participation such as reading with their child at home, encouraging writing activities, and maintaining communication with teachers greatly enhances a student's literacy development. When families show interest and provide support, children become more motivated, confident, and consistent in practicing these skills. This topic highlights how a strong partnership between home and school can lead to better learning outcomes, especially in the early years like Grade 2, where foundational literacy is being built. Parental and family involvement plays a critical role in enhancing reading and writing development among Grade 2 learners. According to Teacher 1, parents who actively engage in reading with their children or serve as role models for reading and writing habits positively influence literacy growth. Similarly, Teacher 2 emphasized that family members provide essential support in reinforcing learning at home. However, in the absence of such collaborative involvement, students may experience limited time and encouragement to develop these foundational skills, which could delay their progress. Parental involvement plays a crucial role in developing children's early lit-

Fig. 4. Emerging Themes on the Teachers’ Cope with the Challenges in Reading and Writing Literacy of Grade 2 Students

eracy skills. Studies show that parents’ active participation in reading and writing activities at home positively impacts children’s literacy development (Pratomo Muryanti, 2020). Key factors influencing children’s reading interests include providing reading materials, allocating time for reading, and encouraging reading aloud (Kiyawa, 2020). Parental involvement is particularly impactful for children receiving less classroom reading instruction. However, so-

cioeconomic factors can affect parents’ ability to engage in their children’s education (Gay et al., 2020). Early engagement in writing activities with parents is crucial in shaping children’s writing identities and methods. Overall, parental involvement contributes significantly to children’s literacy skills development, emphasizing the need to consider both home and school influences on children’s reading and writing abilities.

3.3. Educators’ Insights on Grade 2 Students Reading and Writing Skills—The perspectives and observations of teachers regarding the literacy development of young learners in Grade 2. Educators share their experiences on how students are progressing in reading comprehension, writing abilities, and overall language development at this stage. These insights often include effective teaching strategies, the challenges students face, and the factors influencing their literacy growth, such as home environment, learning disabilities, and classroom resources. Educators

may also discuss the importance of fostering a love for reading and writing at this age to build a strong foundation for future learning. Below are the themes and responses of teachers with regards to their insights on reading and writing skills of grade 2 students.

3.3.1. Recognizing the Needs of every Students—The importance of understanding and addressing the unique learning requirements of each student. Every student has distinct strengths, challenges, interests, and learning styles, and recognizing these differences al-

lows teachers to provide more effective and personalized instruction. This could include tailoring lessons, offering additional support to struggling students, providing enrichment for advanced learners, or using different teaching methods like visual aids, hands-on activities, or collaborative learning. By acknowledging individual needs, educators can create an inclusive and supportive classroom environment where all students can thrive and reach their full potential. When it comes to the learning process, it is not enough for the instructor to just transfer the material, or what is more frequently referred to as the transfer of knowledge. Because there are various components of learning that need to be assessed by teachers on their pupils, including cognitive aspects, emotional aspects, and psychomotor aspects. This is because learning encompasses all of these characteristics. Therefore, in order to realize learning goals with the best possible results, it is necessary for teachers to have an understanding of the peculiarities of each student. We are going to discover that individual variation is typically the result of the simultaneous interplay between hereditary factors and environmental impacts, which finally results in the production of a one-of-a-kind human person. In order to be an effective educator, one must have the ability to comprehend the qualities and features of each unique pupil. In a certain manner or approach, and then directly implement it in the learning process, so that they are aware of the differences between their pupils and how to overcome them in ways that are simple for students to grasp or understand.

3.3.2. Collaborating with the Family—Creating a strong, supportive relationship between educators and families to enhance a child's educational development. When teachers and parents work together, they can share valuable insights about the child's progress, strengths, and areas of improvement. This collaboration can include regular communication through meetings, phone calls, or newsletters,

as well as involving parents in school activities, assignments, and providing them with strategies to support their child's learning at home. By fostering this connection, children receive consistent support that helps improve their reading, writing, and overall academic performance. Collaborative efforts between teachers and parents or guardians play a vital role in enhancing literacy development among Grade 2 learners. Teacher 2 emphasized that involving families in the child's literacy journey fosters a supportive home environment that strengthens learning and encourages academic success. Teacher 3 echoed this by highlighting the importance of home-based tasks in assessing student progress, stating that regular communication with parents through chat allows for updates on both learning capacity and behavioral development. Additionally, Teacher 4 cited the conduct of homeroom meetings as a concrete example of parent-teacher collaboration, where parents are informed about their child's progress in literacy, ensuring alignment between home and school efforts. Research highlights the importance of strong partnerships between educators and families in supporting children's educational and social-emotional development. Effective collaboration enhances children's wellbeing, behavior, and school adjustment (Pirchio, 2023). Key elements of successful partnerships include open communication, resource sharing, and parental involvement in school activities (Cici Supriadi, 2024). Educators' confidence in engaging with families varies, with many feeling less prepared to address parental concerns or work with families facing significant stressors. The quality of parent-educator relationships is positively associated with the frequency of contact, perceived support, and the educational value attributed to early childhood experiences (Pirchio, 2023). Furthermore, collaborative efforts between parents and teachers play a crucial role in fostering children's resilience, enabling them to thrive in challenging circumstances and achieve healthy

development. Ongoing support and training for educators can improve their skills in partnering with families (Murphy et al., 2021). Parental involvement in children's schooling has been attracting increasing attention in developmental psychology. The parent-teacher partnership has been identified as having an important role in children's development. It will help student to be more motivated, happy, and feel supported.

3.3.3. *Modifying Approaches is a Must*—The necessity for educators to be flexible and adaptable in their teaching methods to meet the diverse needs of their students. Since every learner has unique strengths, challenges, and learning styles, modifying teaching approaches ensures that all students can engage with the material and make progress. This might involve adjusting lesson plans, using different instructional strategies, or offering various learning materials to accommodate students with different abilities or backgrounds. By modifying approaches, teachers can create an inclusive learning environment that supports the success of every student, fostering both their academic and personal growth. To effectively meet the diverse learning needs of Grade 2 students, teachers adapt their instructional methods to accommodate varying learning paces and abilities. As highlighted by Teacher 2, modifying teaching approaches enables the creation of a more inclusive and supportive learning environment that addresses the individual needs of all learners. Teacher 5 further elaborated on this practice by explaining that instructional strategies are adjusted based on students' evaluation results. When assessments indicate a need for change, the teacher promptly modifies their approach to ensure more effective learning outcomes. The necessity for educators to be flexible and adaptable in their teaching methods is crucial to meet diverse student needs. Vaughn et al. (2021) argue that adaptive teaching is essential for effective instruction, challenging the reliance on prescriptive curricula that fail to address stu-

dents' linguistic, cultural, and instructional requirements. Similarly, Obidovna (2023) emphasizes the importance of adapting teaching methods to modern educational trends, considering technological advancements and evolving student needs. Baer (2021) highlights the value of flexibility in one-shot library instruction, where librarians must quickly adapt to unfamiliar class dynamics and student abilities. All three studies stress the significance of pedagogical adaptability in creating more relevant and effective learning experiences. They advocate for moving away from restrictive curricula and towards more responsive teaching approaches that can better support diverse student populations (Baer, 2021). Teachers usually modify their teaching approaches depending on the student's need in learning style for them to blend with others and to be more engage in their respective classes.

3.3.4. *Engaging is Utmost Importance to Students*—Actively involving students in the learning process is crucial for their academic success and development. When students are engaged, they are more likely to be motivated, retain information, and develop a deeper understanding of the material. Engaged students actively participate in lessons, ask questions, collaborate with peers, and take responsibility for their learning. Teachers can foster engagement by using interactive teaching methods, incorporating technology, creating a supportive classroom environment, and relating the content to students' interests. Prioritizing student engagement helps ensure that learning is not just passive but meaningful and enjoyable, leading to better outcomes and a lifelong love of learning. Student engagement is a critical element in the learning process, as emphasized by several teachers. According to Teacher 1, teaching becomes ineffective in the absence of student interest thus, it is the teacher's responsibility to foster motivation and ensure learners are actively involved in all aspects of the learning journey. Teacher 2 supported this view,

Fig. 5. Teachers’ Insights in Supporting Reading and Writing Literacy of Grade 2 Students

highlighting that student engagement, motivation, and active participation are key factors in attaining academic success. These elements collectively contribute to meaningful learning experiences and improved educational outcomes. Active student involvement is crucial for academic success and development. It enhances cognitive engagement, facilitates understanding, and promotes academic achievement. Engaging students physically, mentally, emotionally, and intellectually through approaches like Learning by Doing and Problem-Based Learning helps develop 21st-century skills (Sibarani Nurdin, 2023). Student involvement reflects the effectiveness of academic, social, and professional orientation in higher education, contributing to academic success and professional self-realization (Melnichuk Belogash, 2023). Teachers play a vital role as facilitators and activity managers, guiding students towards learning goals. Additionally, parental involvement

significantly impacts student outcomes, including academic achievement and attitudes towards learning. It enhances motivation, self-esteem, and fosters positive parent-child relationships (Sharma, 2024). Creating a supportive school environment that encourages both student and parental participation is essential for maximizing academic success and overall development. The behavioral, academic, emotional, and cognitive involvement of students in learning depends on various factors of the educational environment, including the choice of conceptual approaches to teaching, the level of students’ linguistic and communicative competences. The students’ involvement in the educational process in education reflects the effectiveness of the academic, social, and professional orientation of education, which contributes to academic success and professional self-realization of students.

4. Implications and Future Directions

This study explored the barriers to reading and writing development among grade school learners as perceived by teachers. The findings highlight key challenges that hinder literacy growth, including limited resources, varying student readiness, and gaps in instructional support. These insights offer valuable implications for improving literacy instruction, informing educational policies, and guiding future interventions aimed at fostering foundational language skills.

4.1. Findings—The findings of this study align with the principles of Constructivist Theory and Bronfenbrenner’s Ecological Systems Theory, as proficient teachers identified both instructional and environmental barriers to reading and writing development in Grade 2 learners. From the constructivist perspective, teachers observed that learners struggled due to limited engagement in meaningful, interactive learning experiences, highlighting the need for more student-centered and hands-on literacy approaches. Meanwhile, the ecological lens was evident in how external factors such as lack of parental support, socioeconomic difficulties, and limited access to reading materials at home were seen to significantly impact learners’ literacy growth. These insights imply that effective interventions must address both in-class teaching strategies and the broader systems surrounding the child, emphasizing the importance of collaborative efforts among teachers, families, and communities to support foundational literacy skills.

4.2. Implications—This study also shows how important it is for teachers to take action and adjust to their students’ needs. Many teachers make and change their own materials to match what the curriculum asks for and what their students can actually do. But often, they do this without enough resources or help from the school. Because of this, teachers carry the heavy responsibility of finding ways to help students catch up, which shows that there is a strong need for more support from the education system in teaching reading and writing. The experiences shared by seasoned teachers also

point to the significance of early interventions and differentiated instruction. Recognizing that student progress at different rates, effective literacy development requires flexible teaching strategies, individualized support, and regular assessment. Addressing the root causes of reading and writing difficulties from an early age can significantly enhance long-term academic success.

4.3. Future Directions—To address the identified barriers and support the development of literacy skills among grade learners, the following recommendations are proposed: Teachers Professional development programs must be continuous and focused on evidence-based literacy instruction strategies, including phonics, guided reading, and scaffolded writing exercises. Equipping teachers with updated pedagogical tools will allow them to meet the diverse literacy needs of their learners. School Administrators Schools should prioritize creating a print-rich environment and allocate time within the school day specifically for reading and writing activities. Investing in libraries, classroom reading corners, and writing workshops can create an immersive literacy culture. Policymakers Educational policy must support early grade literacy by funding resources such as reading kits, assessment tools, and instructional materials tailored to local contexts. Policies should also mandate literacy benchmarks to track student progress and guide curriculum planning. Community Community involvement plays a vital role in supporting literacy. Parents and guardians should be engaged through literacy programs that encourage reading at home. Lo-

cal organizations and volunteers can contribute by organizing reading sessions or donating materials to schools. Future Researchers This study focused on teachers' perspectives. Future research may explore learners' experiences and challenges in reading and writing development to gain a more balanced understanding.

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